

INTERVIEW SCRIPT – Software Testing

Thank you very much for deciding to be part of the study.

Introduction

The main focus of our interview today is to understand, from **your perspective**, how do you approach testing. This interview forms a part of a set of interviews that we are conducting in order to understand human thought process in functional testing. We understand that your approaches and handling of a test-task for your company is confidential, thus this interview may contain sensitive data. We therefore are going to use this interview for data collection that will be used for understanding your approach towards testing in an anonymous form.

The interview will be recorded and transcribed (as previously agreed). At any point during the interview you can request to go **off the record** (to stop recording the interview). After the interview, the confidentiality of the material will be dealt with the following protocol.

| [Terms of Confidentiality Agreement]

We shall try to limit the **interview time** to **1.5 hours**. During the interview we will go through a set of context related questions, questions concerning your role/work in the company, and questions regarding your devising of strategy for performing testing in **Company-ICT**. It would be good if you can provide examples from your work/experience to support your answers. There are no right or wrong answers.

Any questions before we begin?

Interview Questions

Around
 70
Minutes

A NOTE FOR INTERVIEWER

Start the interview recording.

Less than
 10
Minutes
Elapsed
 10

1. WARM-UP QUESTIONS:

Q1.1: Tell us something about your work experience?

- ✓ *How long have you been with Company-ICT?*
- ✓ *Which role are you presently working in, and in which domain?*
- ✓ *How long have you been working in this role?*
- ✓ *What other positions/roles' experience have you had in the past? Have you worked in this domain before, and when?*

- ✓ *What kinds or level of testing do you perform?*
[unit, integration, system testing, regression, sanity, smoke, etc.]
- ✓ *What other kinds or level of testing have you performed earlier, and when?*
- ✓ *Do you perform manual or automated testing (which one have you performed earlier and for how long)?*

2. GENERAL QUESTIONS:

Around

⌚ 20

Minutes

Elapsed

⌚ 30

Q2.1: Can you summarize what you have to do as a Developer/Tester (for example typical tasks, duties, etc. that you perform)?

- ✓ *How do you ensure the quality of the task in hand (e.g., walk me through the process)?*
- ✓ *What kind of artefacts do you produce and in what sequence (can you please, name the artefacts)?*
- ✓ *How much time does each artefact require?*
- ✓ *Does your test-suite/artefacts go through a review?*
 - *What kind of changes are suggested, more behaviour/code confirming or behaviour/code breaking?*
 - *Do these changes impact your behaviour (of code-confirmation or code breaking) while accommodating review requests into the artefact?*
- ✓ *Do you use any tool to support your testing and what kind of support does that tool provide?*
 - *Do you think the tool supports or prompt code-confirming or code-breaking behaviour in some way?*

3. OBSERVATION QUESTIONS:

Q3.1: How do you approach a module for testing?

- ✓ *How are the requirements communicated to you (written or verbal), do you try to improve the quality of requirements, e.g., incorporating the possible unhappy scenarios through testing or making it part of the requirements*
- ✓ *Do you follow any process(es) for performing testing (e.g., organisation defined OR Team defined OR Own practice)?*
- ✓ *How do you design test-cases?*
 - *What is your approach when you design test-cases (code-confirming or code breaking)?*
 - *Which one do you prefer to take a start with (code-confirming or code breaking)?*
 - *Is code-breaking or code-confirming approach like a chained behaviour (How do you switch to the other)?*
- ✓ *What is your approach when you retest a module (e.g., after post release defects, after accommodating change requests)? When you re-test a module/patch after post-release defects; do you focus on confirming module's behaviour, or do you focus more on testing erroneous or unanticipated situations?*
- ✓ *Do you think, the type of testing you perform influences your testing approach, e.g., encouraging more code confirming or code-breaking testing strategy (and how)?*
- ✓ *Does test-suite execution prompt code-confirming or code-breaking behaviour?*
- ✓ *When are you satisfied with your own testing?*

Around

⌚ 30

Minutes

Elapsed

⌚ 60

Note: [If an Interviewee is a Developer]

Q3.2: Which methodologies (method) do you use for development, or have used earlier?

- ✓ *Do you think, the current methodology (or the ones in past) influence your testing, e.g., when you are designing and executing test-cases?*
- ✓ *Primarily for breaking the code or confirming its expected behaviour?*
 - *Which one do you go for initially?*

Note: [If an Interviewee is a Tester]

Q3.2: The types or level of testing you use...? (in reference with above answers)

- ✓ *Do you just confine yourself to black-box testing or e.g., consider grey box testing, too?*
 - *Do you think it affects the approach towards code-breaking or code-confirming?*

Q3.3: Have you ever had any kind of trainings regarding testing?

- ✓ *e.g., how to perform testing?*
- ✓ *How to think in a certain way for testing?*
- ✓ *Or have been taught development methodology that values testing, especially code-breaking techniques?*

Q3.4: How in your opinion earlier familiarity with the domain influence your testing approach?

- ✓ *When you are familiar with the domain already, do you first prefer to test the specified requirements or try to test the scenarios that developers usually forget to handle?*
- ✓ *How is your approach when you are not familiar with the domain? Do you try to develop a necessary understanding of the domain first or begin validating the behaviour according to the requirements?*

Q3.5: When is some task difficult for you (from the perspective of testing particularly)?

- ✓ *Does this effect your testing approach / testing activity in some way? For example, do you then prefer to confirm the requirements first or go for code-breaking testing approach?*

Q3.6: Do you think other factors (e.g., urgency, time-pressure, performance, peer pressure) affect your testing?

- ✓ *How do you define time-pressure/performance/peer pressure? Or when do you think, you are under time-pressure/performance/peer pressure?*
- ✓ *And how?*
- ✓ *For example, when you are under time-pressure/performance/peer pressure; how does it affect code confirming/breaking behaviour, and to what extent?*
- ✓ *How do you define performance for yourself? Or are there some company set standards for performance? How does this effect your work in context of testing?*

4. WRAP-UP QUESTIONS:

Q4.1: Any other factors or point that we missed but you would like to reflect on, that effect testing? In the context.

- ✓ *For example, promoting code-breaking or code validating behaviour.*
- ✓ *Are those minor or serious factors, in your opinion?*
- ✓ *Some practice from the past that you would like to refer that in your opinion promotes code-breaking or code-confirming behaviour? (if the participant has an earlier experience or practices have been changed over the time)*

A NOTE FOR INTERVIEWER

Around
⌚ **10**
Minutes
Elapsed
⌚ **70**

Around
⌚ **1**
Minutes
Elapsed
⌚ **71**

Stop the interview recording.

Closing Remarks.